

Supplement Material: Criteria for Effective Site Selection of Direct Air Capture and Storage Projects

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Stakeholder assessment and stakeholder definition

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) is a strategy aimed at capturing CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel point sources and transporting them to geological storage sites, preventing 90-95% of the CO₂ from entering the atmosphere. It is important to note that CCS is not a carbon dioxide removal (CDR) measure. However, Direct Air Capture and Storage (DACs) and CCS can utilize the same infrastructure for CO₂ transportation and geological storage. While DACs is a relatively new and underdeveloped technology, there have been previous attempts at CCS projects that were ultimately cancelled due to opposition from civil groups [1]. The debate around CCS in Germany came to an end when CO₂ storage was prohibited [2]. Given the similarities between DACs and CCS, and the novelty of DACs in Germany, the stakeholder analysis primarily focused on stakeholders who played a significant role in the previous CCS debate. Additional stakeholders involved in the deployment and development of DACs were also identified through web searches, media analysis, and scientific literature. These stakeholders include communities, NGOs, individuals, companies, government parties, officials, and other groups directly or indirectly affected by or influencing the implementation of carbon capture technologies. The stakeholders were then categorized into groups based on their characteristics and roles. These groups are:

- Society: Citizens, communities, or groups of citizens playing a major role in the implementation of CCS and/or DACs in Germany or being affected, either negatively or positively, by its implementation.
- Research: Scientists, research institutes or groups of scientists developing CCS and/or DACs or influencing its implementation.
- Government - EU: Politicians, groups of politicians or organisms of the European Union's government currently or formerly influencing the implementation of CCS and/or DACs.
- Government - National: Politicians, groups of politicians or parties of the German federal government currently or formerly influencing the implementation of CCS and/or DACs.

- Government - Sub-national: Politicians, groups of politicians or parties of any of the 16 states of the German Federal Republic currently or formerly influencing the implementation of CCS and/or DACS.
- Government - Local lever: Politicians, groups of politicians or parties of any of the 294 districts or 106 district-free cities of the German Federal Republic currently or formerly influencing the implementation of CCS and/or DACS.
- Economic sector: Individuals, companies or groups of individuals or companies belonging to any of the three-sectors of German economy (extraction, manufacturing, and service) having no direct involvement in the development or implementation of CCS and/or DACS but influencing its implementation or being affected, either negatively or positively, by its implementation.
- Industry: Individuals, companies, and groups of companies currently or formerly influencing the development and implementation of CCS and/or DACS in Germany.
- Non-governmental organizations (NGO): Independent organizations such as non-profit entities, clubs, associations, and lobby groups currently or formerly influencing the implementation of CCS and/or DACS in Germany.
- Energy sector: Individuals, companies and groups of companies involved in the production and sale of energy formerly or currently influencing the implementation of CCS and/or DACS in Germany. This group includes the fossil fuel industry, electrical power industry, nuclear power industry, and renewable energy industry.
- DAC(S) Company: Companies or groups of companies developing and/or implementing CCS and/or DACS in Germany and abroad.

Comprehensive criteria-set for DACS site assessment

The comprehensive criteria set for conducting a multi-criteria DACS site assessment was developed through an extensive analysis of literature and consultation with experts from various disciplines. This approach ensured a thorough evaluation of site suitability while incorporating the perspectives of relevant stakeholder groups. Each criterion is supported by relevant literature and accompanied by an explanation or description of its significance. It should be noted that while these criteria expand upon the existing academic and policy literature, it may not encompass every possible criterion. Initially, the criteria were categorized into ten groups, including technical DAC criteria, technical storage criteria, innovation economic criteria, business economic criteria, regional economic criteria from a policymaker's perspective, regional air quality criteria, unintended climate impacts/counter-effect criteria, acceptance criteria, legal criteria, and environmental criteria. Through this process, a total of 73 individual criteria were identified and can be found in Table 1, along with the rationale behind their selection.

Table 1: Comprehensive criteria-set for DACS site assessment (with aggregated categories 1 - Climate, Energy, and Infrastructure Requirements, 2 - Financial and Economic Considerations, 3 - Political, Legal, and Institutional Readiness, 4 - Environmental Factors and Climate Impact, 5 - Public Attitudes, Perception, and Acceptance)

Number	Category	Criteria	Description/explanation	Reference	Aggregated category
1	Technical DAC Criteria	Performance in prevailing climatic conditions	Prevailing climatic conditions (temperature and humidity) impact the performance and energy requirement of different technical DAC solutions in different ways.	[3], [4], [5]	1
2	Technical DAC Criteria	Sufficient amount of renewable electrical energy available (measured by load factor)	Operating a DAC plant requires high amounts electricity, to provide CDR this needs to be renewable sources.	[5]	1
3	Technical DAC Criteria	Sufficient amount of renewable heat at respective temperature level available	Most DAC processes need heat for the desorption step, to provide CDR this needs to be renewable sources.	[5]	1
4	Technical DAC Criteria	Sufficient amount of renewable cooling available	Some DAC processes need cooling after the desorption step, to provide CDR this needs to be renewable sources.	[5]	1
5	Technical DAC Criteria	Water availability	Some DAC processes need water to run properly.	[5]	1

6	Technical DAC Criteria	Land eligibility	It needs to be allowed to build the DAC plant on the intended land (no natural reserve e. g.)		1
7	Technical DAC Criteria	Existing transportation infrastructure	In case capturing and storage is not happening at the same site, transportation infrastructure is needed.	[6]	1
8	Technical DAC Criteria	Distance to storage site	In case capturing and storage is not happening at the same site the distance between storage and capture needs to be overcome by transportation infrastructure.		1
9	Technical storage criteria	Storage capacity	Depending on the amount of CO ₂ needed to be stored	[7]	1
10	Technical storage criteria	Storage safety (seismicity, ground water effects)	Site selection based on health, safety, and environmental risk	[8]	1
11	Technical storage criteria	Reservoir scale assessment	Considers key reservoir properties which could change significantly from site to site (continuity, thickness, lithology, facies, porosity, permeability, storage depth, etc.).	[9]	1
12	Technical storage criteria	Regional scale assessment	Considers the potential factors which could impact the reservoir quality across a region (depositional environment, structure, diagenesis, surface changes).	[9]	1
13	Innovation economic criteria	Lobbying activities can significantly impact the success	Lobbying efforts can help shape policies, regulations, and funding opportunities	[10], [11], [12]	3

		and adoption of DAC technology.	that are favorable to DACS development and deployment.		
14	Innovation economic criteria	Existing networks and associations play a vital role in the success of DAC initiatives.	Collaborating with and leveraging the connections and resources within these networks can support knowledge sharing, funding opportunities, and overall growth of the DACS industry.	[12]	3
15	Innovation economic criteria	Supporting the stimulation for positive expectations involves fostering a positive perception and outlook towards DAC technology.	This can be achieved through public education initiatives, showcasing successful case studies, and highlighting the potential benefits of DACS for climate change mitigation and sustainable development.	[12]	3
16	Innovation economic criteria	Networking activities, including international cooperations and refocusing of existing networks, are essential for knowledge exchange, sharing best practices, and driving innovation in the DAC field.	Collaborating with international partners and optimizing existing networks can accelerate the development and deployment of DACS technology.	[12]	3
17	Innovation economic criteria	Early signs and announcements play a crucial role in creating awareness and generating interest in DAC technology.	By providing early indications and announcements about the development of DACS projects, it can attract investors and stakeholders while also encouraging further research and innovation in the field.		3

18	Business economic criteria	Availability of low-cost renewable electrical energy sources is an important factor for the economic viability of DAC projects.	Access to affordable renewable electricity can help reduce operational costs and improve the overall cost-effectiveness of DAC technology.	[13]	2
19	Business economic criteria	Availability of low-cost renewable heat energy sources is crucial for certain DAC processes that require heat for the desorption step.	Access to affordable renewable heat can contribute to the overall cost efficiency and sustainability of DAC operations.	[13]	2
20	Business economic criteria	Availability of low-cost renewable cooling energy sources is necessary for specific DAC processes that require cooling after the desorption step.	Having access to affordable renewable cooling can help optimize the energy consumption and operational costs of DAC plants.	[13]	2
21	Business economic criteria	Availability of low-cost water resources is important for DAC processes that require water.	Access to affordable water resources can contribute to the overall cost efficiency and sustainability of DAC operations.	[13]	2
22	Business economic criteria	Low uncertainty in energy price is beneficial for DAC projects as it allows for better cost predictability and financial planning.	Having a stable and low uncertainty in energy prices reduces the risk of unexpected cost fluctuations and assists in ensuring the long-term economic viability of the DACS operation.	[13]	2
23	Business economic criteria	Availability of low-cost transport / energy infrastructure	Access to transport and energy infrastructure can contribute to the overall cost efficiency and sustainability of DACS operations.	[13]	2

24	Business economic criteria	Other cost in the context of CAPEX/OPEX	labor / manufacturing / land / raw material & resources / construction / leasing costs etc.	[13]	2
25	Business economic criteria	Proximity to relevant suppliers & markets/customers (and competitors and parent company's facilities)	Proximity to suppliers, for example, can contribute to the overall cost efficiency and sustainability of DACS operations.	[13]	2
26	Business economic criteria	Having access to a local labor force with specific characteristics, such as the required skill levels, is essential for the successful implementation of DAC projects.	The availability of skilled workers in the area can significantly contribute to the efficiency and productivity of the operation.	[13]	2
27	Business economic criteria	Business-friendliness of host government and local public authorities	Tax incentives/benefits and other privileges (vs. tax and duty burden, administrative barriers)	[13]	2
28	Business economic criteria	General economic factors of the destination location/country	e.g., GDP / unemployment rate, strength of currency, geopolitical and economic conditions etc.	[13]	2
29	Business economic criteria	Legal and regulatory framework for business activities	Legal system (incl. e.g., investor protection), environmental regulations, compensation laws etc.	[13]	3
30	Business economic criteria	Good governance	Government stability and structure, consistency of government policy	[13]	3
31	Business economic criteria	Social conditions / living standard in the region/country	Education system, crime rate etc.	[13]	3

32	Regional economic criteria from a policy maker's perspective	Potential environmental damages	e.g., water shortage, additional land use / soil sealing	Relevant criteria in terms of cost-benefit-evaluation of (public) investment projects from a welfare perspective (see literature on cost-benefit analysis: [14], [15] etc.; in addition: Guide to Cost-benefit-Analysis by European Commission [16])	4
33	Regional economic criteria from a policy maker's perspective	Financial outcome	public subsidies / tax exemptions vs. public revenues (income tax etc.)		2
34	Regional economic criteria from a policy maker's perspective	"Local content" effects	additional output / gross value added (incl. labour income) / employment in the region due to CAPEX/OPEX		2
35	Regional economic criteria from a policy maker's perspective	Regional spillover effects	e.g., further industrial settlements following the DACS establishment, regional transfer of know-how / innovations		2
36	Regional air quality criteria	WHO air quality guideline	DAC leakages effect on long-term exposure to key air pollutants	[17], [18]	4
37	Regional air quality criteria	National air quality regulations	DAC leakage's potential role in exceeding (short-term) limits for regulated air pollutants	[19], [20], [21], [22], [23]	4
38	Regional air quality criteria	Hazardous air pollutants	Local and short-term exposure to toxic compounds.	[24]	4
39	Unintended climate impacts	Perturbation of atmospheric radiative budget	Potential effect of DAC leakages on short-lived climate forcers and clouds	[25]	4

40	Unintended climate impacts	Impact on hydrological cycle and extreme events	Potential effect of DAC leakages on precipitation and evapotranspiration	[26], [27]	4
41	Acceptance criteria	Perceived risk	e.g. the belief that CO ₂ storage could cause earthquakes, explosions, leaks, or environmental degradation reduce support	[28], [29]	5
42	Acceptance criteria	Perceived benefits	e.g. the belief that DAC can effectively remove CO ₂ from the atmosphere, provide employment, address climate change, or promote revenues from carbon tax increase support	[28], [29]	5
43	Acceptance criteria	Perceived tampering with nature	Feelings that nature should not be manipulated in such a way reduce support	[28]	5
44	Acceptance criteria	Perceived cost	Higher implementation costs reduce support	[30]	5
45	Acceptance criteria	Subsurface components of DAC (storage)	Rejection of DACS is driven by a concern of the subsurface components (drilling, injection, and mineralization components) more than the surface components (capture)	[29]	5
46	Acceptance criteria	Permanence of storage	The guarantee that CO ₂ will remain stored has a slight effect on support	[30]	5
47	Acceptance criteria	Social norm perception	Some studies have found that the influence of certain social circles, for example friends and family, can influence the individual's support attitude.	[30]	5
48	Acceptance criteria	Pro-DACS attitude	Having a pro DACS attitude by believing	[30]	5

			in its effectiveness and its suitability for long-term CO ₂ storage increases support		
49	Acceptance criteria	Benefits and risk communication	Exposure to information related to the benefits and risks of DACS reduces support	[29]	5
50	Acceptance criteria	Trust	Trust is a positive predictive of support	[29]	5
51	Acceptance criteria	Trust in technology	Because DACS is a new technology trust in relevant actors is necessary. Trust in actors increases support.	[28]	5
52	Acceptance criteria	Trust in political stability and government	Trust in the government and on the political stability of a country are positive predictors of support.	[28], [29], [30]	5
53	Acceptance criteria	Age	Mixed results. Some studies found that Lower age is a predictor of rejection [19] while other reports higher age as a predictor of rejection [20]	[29], [30]	5
54	Acceptance criteria	Education	Higher education is a predictor of rejection	[29], [30]	5
55	Acceptance criteria	Gender	Gender is a determinant of support (males support it more than females)	[28], [29]	5
56	Acceptance criteria	Concern about climate change	Concern about climate change and the need of urgent action increases support	[28], [29]	5
57	Acceptance criteria	Feelings of moral obligation to contribute to climate protection	Feeling responsibility for nature and climate change increases support	[29], [30]	5
58	Acceptance criteria	Renewable powered DAC plant	DAC projects using a higher share of	[30]	5

			renewable energy increase support		
59	Acceptance criteria	Moral hazard	e.g. the belief that DACS will divert money from renewables, encourage fossil fuel economy, or be more expensive than other solutions reduce support	[29]	5
60	Legal criteria	Economic incentive schemes	(e.g., tax reductions, subsidies, integration in compulsory or voluntary carbon markets)	[13], [31], [32]	3
61	Legal criteria	Functioning legal system / legal certainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administrations and courts act in accordance with existing laws • People comply with existing laws • Investment protections is guaranteed 	[13], [32], [33]	3
62	Legal criteria	Legal readiness	<p>Laws must be in place on</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • removal and negative emissions (distinctions and specific goals) • plant approval • plant supervision • the transport of CO₂ • the storage of CO₂ • the re-use CO₂ • creditability in the CO₂ management system • Compensation • Environmental protection requirements: EIA & quality standards for DAC-operations: air, climate, 	[32], [33]	3

			water, and soil; and standards for storage activities		
63	Legal criteria	Functioning administrative structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for the approval and supervision of DAC-plants and operations • accounting of removed and stored CO₂ 	[33]	3
64	Legal criteria	Human rights compliance	Construction and operation of the DAC plants as well as the storage of CO ₂ may touch or even restrict human rights of specific groups of people (e.g., indigenous peoples in Canada)	[31], [33]	3
65	Environmental criteria	GWP reduction potential from a life cycle perspective (incl. supply of energy and materials)	Main objective: Overall GWP reduction will be smaller than DAC capture rate due to supply of energy and materials and leakage (all technologies)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
66	Environmental criteria	Acidification	Some technologies emit acidic emissions, which might be a problem for specific locations (technology specific)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
67	Environmental criteria	Ecotoxicity	Some technologies have emissions which can cause a loss in biodiversity (technology specific)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
68	Environmental criteria	Human toxicity	Some technologies emit chemicals which can cause harm on human health (technology specific)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
69	Environmental criteria	Particulate Matter	Primary particulate matter and precursor emissions by some technologies can have an impact on respiratory systems of humans and	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4

			animals expressed in DALYS (technology specific)		
70	Environmental criteria	Photochemical ozone formation	Formation of summer smog due to some local conditions and emissions during capture (technology specific)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
71	Environmental criteria	Eutrophication	Some technologies emit emissions which cause an increase in nutrient on terrestrial, freshwater or marine ecosystems (technology specific)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
72	Environmental criteria	Land use change	A combination of area needed, time of occupation and land change due to the use (all technologies)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4
73	Environmental criteria	Water scarcity	Combination of water amount, quality of water needed and released and availability (all technologies)	[34], [35], [36], [37], [38], [39], [40]	4

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